

NOTES

7. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **70**, 4488, 1952, **74**, 4744.
8. J. H. YOR and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
9. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3203.

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with *o* Ethylmercaptobenzoic Acid as Primary Ligand and Pyridine and Methylpyridine as Co-ligands

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Manuscript received 4 August 1986, revised 10 September 1987, accepted 23 September 1987

The present investigation reports the synthesis and characterisation of mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *o*-ethylmercaptobenzoic acid, a potential (OS) bidentate ligand as the primary and pyridine and α -picolin as the co-ligands.

mercaptobenzoic acid in minimum volume of dry dimethyl formamide^a. To this solution, ethyl iodide and potassium carbonate were added. The reaction mixture was stirred and allowed to stand overnight. The solution was then poured in ice-water when *o*-EMBH appeared as solid which was recrystallised in ethanol.

The complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with primary ligand (*o*-EMBH) were prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the metal chlorides (0.01 mol) and *o*-EMBH (0.02 mol) at pH $\approx$ 8 for $\sim$ 3 h. The complexes separated on cooling the solution. The complexes were filtered, washed with water, ethanol, ether and finally air-dried at 80°. Cu^{II} complexes were light yellow and the Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were brownish green, reddish yellow and green, respectively. Elemental analyses of the complexes correspond to the general formula M(*o*-EMB)₂(H₂O).

For the preparation of the mixed-ligand complexes, the ethanolic solution of the metal chlorides, the co-ligand (L=pyridine or α -picoline) and *o*-EMBA in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio were refluxed at pH $\approx$ 8 for 6 h. The precipitated complexes were washed with water, ether and finally dried at 80°. Elemental analyses of the complexes correspond to the general formula M(*o*-EMB)₂L, where M=Mn, Co, Ni and Cu.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} [*] B.M.	Λ_m ^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		M	S	N		
1.	Mn ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	11.90 (11.95)	15.00 (15.05)	—	5.84	14.00
2.	Mn ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (Py) ₂	9.32 (9.40)	11.00 (11.15)	4.70 (4.89)	5.84	15.00
3.	Mn ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (α -Pic) ₂	8.10 (8.94)	10.45 (10.59)	4.44 (4.64)	5.80	15.50
4.	Co ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	12.46 (12.88)	13.98 (14.01)	—	5.00	9.5
5.	Co ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (Py) ₂	9.86 (10.16)	10.72 (11.08)	4.11 (4.89)	5.10	8.9
6.	Co ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (α -Pic) ₂	10.56 (10.43)	10.86 (10.68)	9.96 (9.89)	5.08	9.8
7.	Ni ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	12.90 (12.84)	14.11 (14.02)	—	3.10	11.8
8.	Ni ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (Py) ₂	11.01 (10.13)	10.96 (11.06)	4.75 (4.83)	3.08	11.2
9.	Ni ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (α -Pic) ₂	10.36 (10.56)	9.86 (9.96)	4.65 (4.58)	3.06	11.60
10.	Cu ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	13.70 (13.76)	13.70 (13.86)	—	2.01	16.50
11.	Cu ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (Py) ₂	10.76 (10.88)	10.80 (10.97)	4.50 (4.79)	2.00	15.00
12.	Cu ^{II} (<i>o</i> -EMB) ₂ (α -Pic) ₂	10.30 (10.35)	10.44 (10.43)	4.50 (4.56)	2.00	14.90

*At 308 K. **In acetone.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. *o*-Mercaptobenzoic acid (*o*-MBH) was prepared by the reported procedure¹. *o*-Ethylmercaptobenzoic acid (*o*-EMBH) was prepared by dissolving *o*-

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis, molar conductivity and magnetic moment data of the complexes are given in Table I. The low conductivity values of the complexes were indicative of their non-electrolytic

nature. The magnetic moment values^{3,4} of all the complexes were in the normal range. The values for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes correspond that for high-spin octahedral complexes.

The infrared spectra of the free ligand (*o*-EMBH) exhibit band at 3 180 cm⁻¹ due to OH of carboxylic group⁵. This band however disappeared in all the complexes. The absorption at 2 570 cm⁻¹ is assigned⁶ to ν_{COOH} in the free ligand. This band is also not observed in the spectra of the complexes. These data supports the presence of deprotonated carboxylic group in the complexes⁷. The ligand (*o*-EMBH) absorbs at 1 210 and 685 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned^{8,9} to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S-R}}$, respectively. However, $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band is observed at 1 185–1 195 cm⁻¹ in all complexes, which shows coordination through hydroxylic oxygen of carboxylic group. The $\nu_{\text{C-S-R}}$ band is also not observed in the spectra of the complexes, which shows that sulphur is coordinating in all the complexes. The coordination of water molecule in the complexes Sl. nos. 1, 4, 7, 10 (Table 1) was evident by the appearance of a broad hump at 3 450 cm⁻¹. The appearance of a band at 230–280 cm⁻¹ confirms the coordination of nitrogen of pyridine or α -picolin in the complexes. The coordination through oxygen and sulphur was further supported by the appearance of $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ band at 600–625 and 325–340 cm⁻¹, respectively.

The electronic spectra of the mixed-ligand Mn^{II} complexes exhibit three bands of low extinction coefficient at 16 500–17 000, 26 400–27 150 and 28 800–29 000 cm⁻¹ due to transitions ${}^6A_{1g}(G) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ (ν_1), ${}^6A_{1g}(G) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ (ν_2) and ${}^6A_{1g}(G) \rightarrow {}^4E_{1g}(G)$ (ν_3), respectively. Here all the transitions are weak as they are spin-forbidden. The 10 *Dq* (10 300–10 400 cm⁻¹), *B'* (600–650 cm⁻¹) and *B* (0.62–0.67) values are within the range of the values for octahedral Mn^{II} complexes. The mixed ligand Co^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 8 500–8 700, 16 400–17 400 and 20 800–21 100 cm⁻¹ due to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The 10 *Dq* (8 591–9 113.5 cm⁻¹), *B'* (781–825.5 cm⁻¹) and *B* (0.697–0.739) values are quite consistent with the values reported for octahedral structure. The mixed-ligand complexes of Ni^{II} also exhibit three bands at 10 100–10 400, 16 000–16 950 and 25 500–28 400 cm⁻¹ due to transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The 10 *Dq* (10 110–10 330 cm⁻¹), *B'* (777–939 cm⁻¹) and *B* (0.74–0.90) values are consistent with the values reported for octahedral structure.

The visible spectra of Cu^{II} complexes exhibit broad asymmetric band at 12 300–14 875 cm⁻¹. In the case of mixed-ligand complexes of Cu^{II}, all the six ligands are not the same. Hence, crystal field of such complexes are tetragonally distorted and it becomes of *D*_{4h} symmetry as such. Consequently, two degenerate states, *i.e.* 2E_g and ${}^2T_{2g}$ further split up into two components each. Thus three bands at 12 300–14 850, 12 500–14 875 and

12 600–14 875 cm⁻¹ correspond to transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ (ν_1), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ (ν_3), respectively. But due to small energy gap between these components, all the three bands envelop together and a broad symmetrical band is observed. These values are in good agreement with the values reported for distorted octahedral complexes of copper(II).

References

1. R. REVEST, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1962, **40**, 22^a4.
2. S. B. SHARMA, M. K. SINGH and V. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 664.
3. N. KR. ROY and C. R. SAHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23** 486.
4. S. RANDHAWA, B. S. PANNU and S. L. CHOPRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 112.
5. R. N. TICHANE and W. E. BENNETT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 129³.
6. E. GENNICK, W. C. FERNELINS and B. E. DONGLAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 467.
7. N. K. SANKHLA, D. C. SEHGAL and R. K. MEHTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **6**, 99.
8. B. G. F. GARLSON and H. M. IRVING, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 379.
9. R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 121.

Polarographic Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II) with Picolines and Carboxylate Ions

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Manuscript received 27 October 1986, revised 14 April 1987, accepted 23 September 1987

GAUR and Sharma¹ studied polarographically the simple complexes of Cd^{II} with β - and γ -picolines at 30° and concluded that Cd^{II} forms two successive complexes (1 : 1 and 1 : 2) with β -picoline with stability constants, 18.5 $\pm$ 2 and 224 $\pm$ 5 and with γ -picoline three complexes (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) with stability constants 33 $\pm$ 3, 31 $\pm$ 5 and 665 $\pm$ 10. However, in these studies no mention has been made as to the pH at which the study was made as many changes² in a system of complexes may occur when the pH of the solution is changed. A survey of literature³⁻¹⁸ reveals that simple complexes of Cd^{II} with a number of carboxylate ions, such as formate, oxalate, tartrate, succinate, citrate, malonate and maleate have been studied polarographically. However, the mixed complexes of Cd^{II} with these acids and picolines have not been studied so far. The present study therefore seeks to undertake comprehensive polarographic studies on the mixed complexes of Cd^{II} with β - and γ -picolines, and some carboxylate ions, *viz.* oxalate, malonate, succinate and tartrate.